

THE ROLE OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM ORGANIZED IN
UZBEKISTAN RELIGIOUS EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE
EDUCATION OF YOUTH AND THE SUBJECT OF "TARBIYA"

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Abstract: On the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the subject "Tarbiya" was implemented in general secondary educational institutions starting from the 2020-2021 academic year. This subject, as a component of the concept of continuous spiritual education, inculcates the ideas of national revival and progress in schoolchildren, develops them as people who succeed in life, and provides active citizenship views, responsibility, duty, legal awareness, culture, a broad worldview, healthy religious ideas, enlightenment, and harmony.

Key words: Tashkent, Movarounnahr, Central Asia, Uzbekistan, Education, Islam.

Annotatsiya: "Tarbiya" fani O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining tashabbusi bilan umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida 2020-2021-o'quv yilidan boshlab tatbiq qilindi. Ushbu fan Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasining tarkibiy qismi sifatida maktab o'quvchilarida milliy tiklanish va yuksalish g'oyalarini singdirish, ularni hayotda muvaffaqiyat qozonadigan insonlar sifatida kamol toptirish, faol fuqarolik qarashlari, mas'uliyat, burch, huquqiy ong va madaniyat, keng dunyoqarash, sog'lom diniy tasavvurlar, ma'rifatparvarlik, ahillik kabi ezgu fazilatlarni paydo qilishni asosiy vazifa qilib belgilagan.

Kalit so'zlar: Toshkent, Movarounnahr, Markaziy Osiyo, O'zbekiston, ta'lim, Islom.

Аннотация: По инициативе Президента Республики Узбекистан с 2020-2021 учебного года внедрен предмет «Образование» в учреждениях общего среднего образования. Данный предмет, как составляющая концепции непрерывного духовного образования, прививает школьникам идеи национального возрождения и прогресса, развивает их как успешных

в жизни людей, активные гражданские взгляды, ответственность, долг, правосознание и культуру, широкое мировоззрение. ., определил в качестве основной задачи появление таких хороших качеств, как здоровые религиозные идеи, просвещение и гармония.

Ключевые слова: Ташкент, Мовароуннахр, Средняя Азия, Узбекистан, образование, ислам.

Introduction. Education textbooks were developed under the leadership of the Republican Education Center under the Ministry of Public Education in cooperation with a team of qualified authors consisting of experts, representatives of the education system, and experts in other fields. The experience of developed countries such as Japan, Singapore, England, UAE, China, Korea, Russia, and Germany was used to create a science and textbook system.

The issue of teaching and effectiveness of the science of "tarbiya" should be raised to the level of national affairs. Because the teachers who shape the consciousness, thinking and upbringing of the young generation based on their own knowledge must first of all have spiritual, ideological, social, political and legal knowledge.

Materials and methods. The methods of induction, deduction, simple-to-complex, and complex-to-simple were used in the preparation of this article. The role of the educational system established in the religious educational institutions of Uzbekistan in the education of young people and the science of "Tarbiya" were discussed.

The main part. If we take into account that education is extremely important in the life of any society and country, like water and air, it is inevitable that a country that does not pay enough attention to the education of the young generation will face a crisis. Because for the all-round development of any country, the production of material and spiritual wealth in that country must be carried out without interruption. In order to form such material and spiritual production skills in the young generation, the society must fully understand the importance of teaching education as a separate subject, not only the system of natural works that works efficiently.

In the current socio-economic era, one of the priorities of the education system is to train a qualified specialist with a high culture of thinking, who can make responsible and professional decisions independently, and who can make the right decisions in non-standard situations. Critical thinking, which is part of the education science program, is undoubtedly one of the indispensable skills to

achieve this goal. Moreover, current global challenges show that the acquisition and application of this skill is critical to our survival as a society against various threats.

The lesson of "Tarbiya" should become a curriculum that shows us the richness and priority of feeling, perception and human thinking and teaches us the ways to achieve it. It may not always make sense to include all these features in the field of "Tarbiya" alone. Still, we can't doubt that it's the kind of education that helps us feel human. Especially, young people, after mastering the science of "Tarbiya" and having a good understanding of their capabilities as a result, can try to determine what is important and what is not important, balance various issues, and think about their impact on the modern world.

Along with national traditions, religious values play a very important role in improving the socio-spiritual environment in Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, a lot of work is being done in the field of the country's education system so that the humanistic philosophy and noble ideas of Islam take place in the hearts of young people.

The events happening in the world and in our country and the analysis of the socio-political situation require increasing the productivity of activities in the religious and educational sphere and creating a whole system of training experienced specialists.

Based on these demands and needs, on April 16, 2018, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the religious and educational sphere" was announced.

The human spirit and spirituality elevate the human being to a higher position than other beings. Due to this, in the current era, when the struggle for the minds and hearts of young people is intensifying, the issue of forming a perfect person and restoring historical memory and values are of urgent importance. It is extremely important to explain to every representative of the young generation how important it is to analyze the events that the nation has experienced in its history, to prevent the repetition of mistakes, and to preserve the achievements.

Summary. *The Uzbek people have long been concerned about the future of our country, its well-being, and how our children will grow up to be human beings. For this purpose, social support of the young generation, introducing them to our rich and unique heritage related to the Islamic religion, showing the humane content of our religion, and raising young people to adulthood in the spirit of national pride are set as the main priority. Thus, we can consider that the science*

of "Tarbiya" helps to study the spiritual values of the Uzbek people in close connection with the universal values.

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